

Cryptocurrency/blockchain ideas for speaking topics

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Abstract

Cryptocurrency was designed as a person to person transfer of value beyond bank and governmental control. In addition to honest people, many criminals sought out cryptocurrency as a way to avoid transaction scrutiny by governments to avoid paying taxes while funding illegal enterprises. As a technology-supporting financial executive, I am caught between two worlds: the cryptocurrency I support and my peers who see it as a danger to our global society. My mission is to support cryptocurrency adoption by a wider mainstream society to through compromises made by each faction. Ironically, it will be governments and banks that help advance cryptocurrency through security and regulation. Most people are not good and being their own bank and tracking taxable transactions relative to their local government. I will propose solutions to fix the negative stigma of cryptocurrency and the problems that are holding back widespread adoption.

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